

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Work-life conflict: A study based on nurses in general hospitals in Galle district Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Work-life conflict has become a significant area of research due to the pressures of modern competitive lifestyles, due to that both men and women must earn to support their families. Balancing work and family responsibilities, while maintaining organizational commitment, is especially challenging for nurses, who play a major role in the health sector and often work long hours. This study focuses on the relationship between work-life conflict and organizational commitment among nurses in public sector hospitals in the Galle district in Sri Lanka. The primary objective is to investigate this relationship and understand the factors contributing to work-life conflict, its outcomes, and solutions. The research is quantitative, also use both primary and secondary data. A structured questionnaire was distributed to the random sample of 120 nurses, and the data were analyzed using Excel 2013, with results presented tables, charts and graphs. Findings show a significant negative relationship between work-life conflict and organizational commitment. Nurses must balance their work and family roles to strengthen their psychological bond with their hospitals. Hospital administrations should enhance organizational support to help nurses manage both domains, leading to increased commitment. It is beneficial not only the organization but also the broader society by improving healthcare outcomes.

Key words: Conflict; Organizational Commitment; Work - Life conflict; Work Norms

1. Introduction

Work - life conflict is a most important phenomenon that researches pay their attention in recent times. It can be defined as the role pressure from incompatible work and family domains to create inter role conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 2016). Because of the increase of the women participation to the work force the work - life conflict has become a main issue in the modern world. The revolution saw that in the past the work and family roles defined by sex. According to that the men were drawn to the public domain to work to earn money and the responsibility of private domain was remained with the women. This was reflected by culture even that the men have right to work and women have to take care of the house hold works (Zulfiqar, Muhammad Kundi, Afaq Qureshi, Khan, & Akhtar, 2014). But at the present the traditional gender family roles has changed because of the upturn number in working women. The women are the most suffering party from the work - life conflict because they have more house hold responsibilities than men such as child caring, support husband's work and caring old parents like wise. Not only the women but also men have to share the personal life activities with women because of the traditional gender role changes. This transformation have affected to the work family demands of the work force. Therefore the modern workforce including both men and women have to face the work - life conflict

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Boles et al.(2016) concluded that the work family conflict has several negative outcomes such less commitment, emotional exhaustion and burnout. Work family conflict cannot be separated from organizational commitment of the employees, because it is related with the job and role of the employees they perform formally in their professional life. While it can be described as the employees' feeling of responsibility to the mission of the organization. Further commitment is the feeling of internalized pressure to behave in a way that helps to meets organizational goals and objectives . Thompson, Beauvais, and Lyness (1999) concluded that there was a relationship between high work- life conflict and lower organizational commitment. According to that because of the work - life conflict increase the organizational commitment decrease. According to Spence Laschinger et al. (2001) organizational commitment is critical to both organization and the employees and it is considered as an important component to determine the performance and effectiveness of employees and the organization. So that's why the researchers pay their attention to investigate the relationship between the work - life conflict and organizational commitment.

When consider the previous researches done about this topic, most of them are done in the foreign context such as India, Pakistan, Turkey, America, China and Nigeria like wise. When compare the Sri Lankan context with these countries there are significant differences can be seen in relation to the culture, economy, technology and work structure. Because of that there is a challenge to directly apply the findings from these contexts to Sri Lanka. Therefore, the generalizability is questionable. As well as there is an inconsistency between the findings from different context according to the literature. Netemeyer, Boles, and McMurrian 1996 ; Perrewé, Ralston, and Fernandez 1995 found that there is a negative but significant correlation between work-family conflict and organizational commitment and both variables are inversely correlated. Perrewé, Ralston, and Fernandez (1995) found that this result sustained in the Chinese sample also. But they found that there is no substantial relationship between work - life conflict and organizational commitment in the sample of Americans. Therefore, it is essential to investigate the relationship between work - life conflict and organizational commitment in the Sri Lankan context.

Thus the purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between work - life conflict and organizational commitment among Nurses in General Hospital, Galle , Sri Lanka.

1.1. Research Problem

Health is considered as the most important phenomenon in today's world which determines the wealth of the country. Therefore, health care sector is most important for the country. When consider the health care system in Sri Lanka, it has free and universal health care system to all citizens. Now a day the demand for the health care in Sri Lanka is constantly increasing due to aging population, changing life style factors such as high level of exposure to alcohol, tobacco and increasing the education and awareness about the health. To fulfill that demand the health care in Sri Lanka organized through public and private sector. Therefore, there is a huge competition exists in this industry. To face this competition by achieving organizational goals and objectives human resources of the organization are very important.

There are number of employees in the hospitals such as doctors, nurses, health professionals, and support staff like wise. Nurses can be consider as the largest single group of regulated and registered practitioners in the health workforce of any country and are internationally recognized as being fundamental to the provision of health care (Yamey, 2002) . Hospitals require huge quantity of nurses to provide their services. Nurses have to care the patients, observe and monitor the patient's condition, prepare records, communicate with doctors about the patients and work as operation theatre assistants, health advisors, counselors, supervisors. They are the workers who take care of the patients. Therefore the role of nurse are key to the success of the health care service provided by the hospitals.

If the role of the nurses are important to the success of the organization, they have to face many difficulties because of work schedules. They have improper work schedules specially the night works. Also, they have to work long hours and have to report in emergency situations without considering the regular shift. Thus, they have no enough time to spend with the family life especially for the married nurses such as child caring, caring for husband and elder parents. Then it generates stress, pressure and anxiety and ultimately they cannot balance their work and family life and this will create work - life conflict.

work family conflict has several negative outcomes such as less commitment, emotional exhaustion and burnout (Boles et al., 2016). Commitment from the nurses is essential to the organizational success. The study of organizational commitment of nurses in relation to work - life conflict is very important(Burke & Greenglass, 1999). There are significant difference between committed and uncommitted nurses, committed nurses are remain present on job, loyal to the organization, and less likely to leave the organization and they are not showing any withdrawal behaviors. On the other hand they are ready to sacrifice their effort on behalf of the organization .while less committed nurses brings

absenteeism and turnover problems. Because of nature of the work schedules especially night works, it is really difficult to get the commitment from nurses.

When they are doing night works they tend to think about their children, husband and other house hold activities. Because mothers are wanted especially for the children at night. So their attention for the work may be less. But it is critical the more attention of work from nurses because of the nature of their work such as taking care of patients especially work as operation theatre assistant. Because of these issues the organizational commitment is essential to provide a better health care service. Otherwise, it will adversely affect to the hospital image and finally it will affect to the society. Because the health of the society is determined by the quality of the health care service provide by the hospitals. Therefore, it is important to examine whether there is a relationship between work –life conflict and organizational commitment.

According to this context it is questionable to search what kind of a relationship between work - life conflict and organizational commitment among Nurses in Hospitals in Sri Lanka.

1.2. Research Questions

- What is the relationship between work-life conflict and organizational commitment among Nurses?
- What are the factors behind work-life conflict among nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district hospitals?
- What are the outcomes of work life conflict among nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district hospitals?
- What would be the solutions for work life conflict among nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district hospitals?

1.3. Research Objectives

The overall objective of this research is to investigate the relationship between the work-life conflict and organizational commitment among Nurses.

1.3.1. Specific Objectives

- To identify the factors behind work-life conflict among nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district hospitals
- To search the outcomes of work life conflict among nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district hospitals
- To recommend the solutions for work life conflict among nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district hospitals

1.4. Research Methodology

1.4.1. Data Collection

Data can be obtained through primary and secondary sources. primary data refers to information obtained first hand by the researcher on the variable of interest for the specific purpose of the study. Sekaran and Bougie (2013) has defined Secondary data as the information gathered from sources already existing. Both data collection techniques will be referred in this research study.

1.4.2. Method of Data Collection

A researcher can conduct the research by using two approaches. It can be qualitative approach or quantitative approach. A deep understanding can be get from the qualitative approach. In Quantitative researches aim to test the existing theories of phenomena. The main purpose is to gather, analysis and measure statistical data. This research also attempts to test existing theory. Because this theory falls on the category of quantitative research .due to that his research will be a qualitative research. The main tool of data collection for the research will be a survey. This research will use primary and secondary data for analysis. Books, magazine articles, wed sites sources already existing and reports were the main secondary sources used to assess the historical background, status and other issues related to the work life conflict and organizational commitment. The main source of primary data will be collected through either Experiment or through Survey. To collect primary data researcher use self-administered questionnaire method and hand delivery method use to distribute questionnaire. Due to the busy work schedules of nurses it is really difficult to conduct individual interview. Therefore the researcher decided to use questionnaire method.120 random nurses in public sector hospitals will be taken as a sample of the research and this sample will be selected from four main government hospitals in Galle district (Karapitiya general hospital, Arachchikanda general hospital, Hikkaduwa general

hospital, Balapitiya general hospital) The researcher expect to collect data by using a prepared questionnaire from the nurses in General Hospitals, Galle .

1.4.3. Data Analysis

The researcher will present Quantitative data in form of pie charts, tables and graphs percentages. Under this study the researcher hope to apply descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis and further more to testing also used excel 2013 version.

1.4.4. Population and Sample

Targeted population is 980 nurses in selected hospitals in Galle district (Karapitiya, Puunangoda, Balapitiya , Hikkaduwa) and the sample is 120.

1.5. Significance of the Study

This research is important for the academic side and as well as for the selected organization. When consider the importance for the academic side, the researcher can implement the theoretical knowledge for the practical usage .Further the researcher can improve the knowledge, can have a proper understanding about the topic, aware about the existing knowledge about the research area, important to enhance the analytical skills, Develop the new understanding, improve the decision making skills by doing this research.

The research findings will significant to the nurses. If the findings of this study prove that the there is a significant relationship between work – life conflict and organizational commitment, the nurses can aware about the importance of balancing their work and family roles to create a psychological bond with their hospital. Ultimately it will affect to reduce the other negative outcomes such as pressure, stress, mental ill-health, job dissatisfaction, marital dissatisfaction and total life dissatisfaction

The hospital administration of General Hospitals, Galle can use these findings to improve the organizational support for the nurses to Balance their two domains of the life to increase the organizational commitment. It will support to strategic decision making process too. The study will provide information to managers to understand the work- life conflict face by the nurse and how it affect to the organizational commitment. Because committed employees positively contributed to the organization compared to less committed employees.

Nurses are most important contributors in the health care sector. The organizational commitment of nurses increase by balancing their work and family roles by using the findings, it will also important to the society as a whole. Because they are mostly contributed to the health of the country by take caring patients. If they work under stress it is not suited for their profession and they should be actively doing their job with pleasant face and kindly heart for the patients.

As well as these research findings importance for the future researchers to conduct the researches and clarify and define the nature of the problem how these two variables work – life conflict and organizational commitment relate to each other what are the measurements and scales , methodology that can apply to finding the research results.

1.6. Limitations of the Study

This research has some limitations when performing this research. Data will be collected within few areas of Galle district. As well as this research should be done within next few months. The study will limited itself to the research focus only the nurses in public sector hospitals only , it focus only on the only type of responding category of nurses, Data accuracy Limited time during working hours , sample size is small comparing to the public sector hospitals of Galle district. And also data was collected through self-administered questionnaire only. Also some nurses do not like to share the truth and the despondence depend on their personal perspectives. Getting information through hospitals in government sector has to be much careful and the researcher should follow their rules, norms and their values throughout the process. In the survey each person may give individual results, but it does not mean that same results belong to the whole population. And it will not always be able to go through all the resources. Researcher may not able to gather all the data that since it will take a lot of time.

2. Literature review

2.1. Introduction

In order to develop theoretical frame work for this study extensive literature review was conducted. This chapter deals with the available literature in relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment. Work life conflict in the Sri Lankan context is rarely discussed in this context. This chapter includes a critical review of the literature and conceptual framework of the study along with the operationalization

2.2. Theoretical Literature

Theory of conflict, to begin with indicated by Karl Marx, may be a theory that society is in a state of interminable conflict since of competition for constrained asserts. Conflict theory holds that social order is kept up by mastery and control (instead of agreement and similarity). Agreeing to conflict theory, those with riches and control attempt to hold on to it by any implies conceivable, mainly by stifling the destitute and feeble. An essential preface of conflict theory is that people and groups inside society will work to maximize their possess benefits. The term 'Conflict' has wide intention. It is subject to diverse elucidations completely different setting. It is for the most part alluding to a mental state of intellect where an individual cannot choose the conduct this way or that way. Sometimes, the term is utilized as a distinction of conclusion between two persons or groups independent of their status within any organization. A number of analysts, utilizing differing hypothetical viewpoints, have experimentally recorded the esteem of conflict for making choices and other central viewpoints of social life. Some scholars as; Amason, 1996; Tetlock et al, 1994; Anderson, 1983; Cosier, 1978; Gruenfeld, 1995; Mason and Mitroff, 1981; Peterson and Nemeth, 1996; Schweiger et al, 1986; George, 1974. (Tjosvold, 1 May 2006)

Johan Galtung who is the principal founder of the peace and conflict studies was defines that conflict is initiated through attitudes, physical behaviors and contradictory goals of enemies (Pathak, 29 Aug 2016).

On the first edition of 'Encyclopedia of Violence, Peace and Conflict, Editor-in-Chief Lester Kurtz wrote that,

"The problem of violence poses such a monumental challenge at the end of the 20th century that it is surprising we have addressed it so in adequately. We have not made much progress in learning how to cooperate with another more effectively or how to conduct our conflicts more peacefully. Instead, we have increased the lethality of our combat through revolutions in weapons technology and military training. The "Encyclopedia of Violence, Peace and Conflict" is shaped to help us to take stock of our knowledge concerning these crucial phenomena" (Kurtz, 2008).The differences within the interests, thoughts, needs, status of people result in a struggle. It is characterized as a clash among people coming about in verbal differences, physical mishandles and pressures. A struggle never gives any arrangement to an issue; instep of fair compounds the circumstance. It leads to disregard among people, hampers the efficiency and people frequently feel demotivated after a battle.It can be a huge problem among nurses in public sector hospitals . they have to maintain their families and also they have to give a good commitment to the organization. having a life balace is very important to manage their day today life. Due to that having a balance work life and a family life is very important to nurses.

2.2.1. Conflict Triangle

Social strife encompasses a broad range of social phenomena: class, racial, religious and communal conflict; riots, rebellions; revolution strikes and civil disorders; marches, demonstration, protest gathering and the like.In 1969, Johan Galtung as a sum of this all definition explained, the nature of conflict including both symmetric and asymmetric conflicts. In the author's opinion, a conflict can be viewed as a Antonia whose sides are represented by A- (Attitude), B - (Behavior) and C - (Contradictions/ context), and is one of the most popular and useful way to investigate and to illustrate the complexities of conflict and the triangle summarizes th elements or dimensions of conflict. This examination is based on the premise that clashes have three major components; the context or circumstance, the behavior of those include and their demeanors. These three components impact each other, thus the bolts driving from one to another.

Figure 1 Galtung's Conflict Triangle

Source: Galtung, 1969

Galtung emphasized that the triangle serves the double purpose of keeping the three apart, and of relating them with the arrows of two-way causation. (Galtung, 1996) The first conflict, through the instruments of behavioral heightening, leads to new incompatibilities, a string of determined conflict produced by acts of physical and verbal violence. Since they are derived their arrangement in isolation will not illuminate the fundamental conflict, but may serve the purpose of de-escalation, and subsequently get ready the ground for understanding the fundamental struggle. Another aspect is the utilize of inferred clashes for bargaining concurring to the common rule that the more issues two parties have in common, the more conceivable outcomes would there be for trading off one problem against the other. But that too constitute and motivating force to engage in damaging behavior. In this whole conflict energetic attitudinal forms moreover take put, with their well-known propensity to create in a parallel mold. There are imperative symmetries in the perception, they are to a few extents reflect pictures of each other, through impersonation. Conflict triangle also shows how conflicts are happening and what is the connection between attitude, contradiction and behaviors. different nurses have different attitudes and behaviors it could be a reason for work life conflicts . By understanding these issues, behaviours, attitudes will help to continue a good work life and a family life.

2.2.2. Work - Life Conflict

Define Work-Life Conflict

Work - life conflict occurs when the demands from one role conflict with the demands from another role. The work — life conflict is the role pressures from incompatible work and family domain which create inter role conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 2016). Role conflict generates when individual have to play two roles in their life and the mismatch between these two roles and their personality traits (Allen, Herst, Bruck, & Sutton, 2000).

According to that work and family are the main two domains of their life and when it creates mismatch between the demands of these two roles create the work — hife conflict. Individual required physical, psychological and social resources to fulfill the demands of their two roles (Greenhaus & Beutell, 2016). When individuals use their resources to fulfill duties in one role, it cause to limit an individual to fulfill responsibilities in other role (ten Brummelhuis & Bakker, 2012). According to that the individuals have higher expectation in one role with substantial demands, it will create role pressures for them to do the obligations of other role (Greenhaus & Beutel, 2016). Modern families have both the work and family domains because of the increase of both dual earner families and single parent families. This transformation challenges the individuals to manage the conflict between work and family domains (Ramarajan & Reid, 2013).

2.2.3. Theories on Work-Life Conflict

Work- Life Conflict Theory

Among different theoretical aspects of work-life conflict, this theory is more contemporary theory that proposed by (Greenhaus & Beutell, 2016). Pickering, (2006) also conducted further studies about this theory. According to that individuals have two domains in their life. They are work and family domains. To perform these different roles requires different level of time, commitment and attention. Therefore, perform in one role limit the number of resources that wanted to perform other role. Because individuals operate with fixed number of resources then it will contribute to conflicts. This theory was identified as work — life conflict theory.

Spill- Over Theory

Spill - over theory is the first social construction tradition theory that explain the work- life conflict. The well-being of one domain of life is transmitted to another domain can be explained as spill- over. As well as spill- over effect can be negative or positive from one domain of life to another domain (Pleck, 1977; Staines, 1980). For an example the pressures from work role have a negative effect to family role vice versa. Main reason for this is the limited and the same resources the individuals have. And they have to use these limited and same resources to do different things in different roles. Then it will create problems. In the late 1970 the researchers found that the women faced spill -over effect from their family role into their work role. The men experienced spill- over effect from their work domain to family domain (Pleck, 1977; Staines, 1980). On the other hand, the positive spill -over effect happening in these two roles can be called as enrichment (Baruch & Barnett, 1986).

It explained that when people perform multiple roles, it will positively affect for their overall well- being (Baruch & Barnett, 1986). They indicated that there were multiple assets from participating multiple roles. Many studies shows that Involvement in multiple roles can yield net gain of physical and mental health. Furthermore, there is positive relation among the number of roles perform and psychological well-being. In here the number of roles implies the experiences they gain from these roles that are affect to the well- being. As well as the earning, rewards, recognition, self -esteem, happiness, satisfaction can also gained from involving work roles are positively affect for the well- being of individuals (Baruch & Barnett, 1986).

2.2.4. Determinants of Work — Life Conflict

Researchers measured work life conflict using many ways. Traditionally at the initial stages work life conflict was measured when the work interfered with family (Greenhaus & Beutell, 2016). After that the researchers found the duality of work —life conflict by considering the both domains of work — life conflict: work interference with family and family interference with work (Duxbury, Higgins, & Mills, 2017)

Work Interference with Family (Work — Family Conflict)

It describes the work life influence to the family life such as the individuals who work long hours will affect to reduce the time they spend with their family and inability to do the family life obligations because of the work duties. Therefore, if a person experiencing a high level of work- family role conflict, then the task, duties, responsibilities in their job role interfering to their family life. Especially the excessive work demands of the work role generate negative family outcomes (Akintayo, 2010b). These negative outcomes are life dissatisfaction, marital dissatisfaction, family dissatisfaction, leisure dissatisfaction.

Family Interference with Work (Family — Work conflict)

It describes the family life influence to the work life. It happens when the individuals spend more times with family rather than the job. Therefore, if a person has more responsibilities in the family life it will interfering to work role they perform in the job. If an employee gives their priority for the welfare of family domain, then it reduces the time and energy to perform the work roles. The Family - work conflict is determined by the negative work outcomes and family demands (Akintayo, 2010b). It will affect to reduce the work outcomes such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, job performance, career success and increase the absenteeism and turnover intention.

2.2.5. Forms of Work — Life Conflict

Time — Based Conflict

Time based conflict occurs the time devoted to one role is limit to participate in another role. Time is a fixed factor therefore the time spend in one role is not available for the other role. Further when person spend his/ her more time

with work activities affect to reduce the time spend in family role. Time based conflict include, number of work hours Extra hours spending in work without informing, shift work and overnight travel on the other hand individual spent more time with family obligations affect to increase negative work outcomes such as absenteeism without informing like wise.

As well as the amount and frequency of overtime and irregular shit work and inflexibility of work schedules also associated with the work- life conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 2016). The tlexible work schedules not enough to reduce work lite conflict specially for working mothers for child caring activities. Both the level of flexibility and the needs of employees are affected to reduce the work- life conflict. On the other hand, personal life responsibilities that require large amount of time also generate work life conflict. The work-life conflict faced by married persons are higher than unmarried persons and also parents experienced higher WLC than non-parents When consider the parents, the child bearing responsibility is the main contributor for work — life conflict (Herman & Gyllstrom, 1977).

Strain - Based Conflict

The strain experienced in one role affect in to interfere with participation in other role can be identified as strain-based conflict. As an example, the strains in work role such as work load pressures, job insecurity has created a psychological spill over from work role to family. On the other hand, the family strain such as marriage problems, children ill-health, problems from old parents have created a spillover from family to work. Therefore, the characteristics which produce strain either family or work role affect to create work-life conflict. Ambiguity in work role positively affect to work — life conflict. As well as lower level of leader support and interaction, psychological and physical work demands, and work-life conflict were positively related (Butler, 2015)

In addition to that work environment changes, participation in boundary spanning activities, mental concentration and stress in communication were also related with work- family conflict(Burke & Greenglass, 1999).On the other hand family life interference to work also cause to create high level of work -life conflict. But if the person have supportive spouse, it may affect to reduce the work –life conflict. As well as if there are differences between women™ career orientation and husbands experience then it will create high level of work- life conflict. Also the difference of attitudes between husband and wife towards the wife's employment status also lead to family tension and finally it will adversely affect to their work roles also (Greenhaus & Beutell, 2016).

Behavior — Based Conflict

The mismatch between the required specific behavioral expectations in two roles affects to occur the behavioral — based conflict. Most times the required behaviors in work role is incompatible with the family role. As a example when we consider about the characteristics of a manager in the work role such as emotional stability, self- reliance, aggressiveness and objectivity are not match to when he interact with family members.

They expect warm, affection, kindness for the person. Then the person cannot adjust to these behavioral changes it will contribute to work —family conflict. In addition to that if the individuals have to perform multiple roles in their work, which can limit the individuals' resources to fulfill the roles of personal life (Dierdorff & Ellington, 2008). Specially the individual who have high degree of personal interactions in their job can also direct to fatigue and it will lead to withdrawal from the family life responsibilities (Dierdorff & Ellington, 2008).

2.2.6. Organizational Commitment

Define Concept of Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment 1s the individual's psychological attachment towards an organization (Jabeen, Behery, & Abu Elanain, 2015). Further organizational commitment as the strength of the individual's feelings of an attachment towards the organization (Meyer, Allen, & Smuth, 1993). In addition 1t can be defined as individual's bond, attachment or linkage to an organization (Klein, Cooper, Molloy, &Swanson, 2014). Employee willingness to stay with organization is reflected by the organizational commitment. Therefore organizational commitment 1s employees' sense of identification, involvement, willingness to stay due to the benefits, feeling of responsibility and based on the affection to the organization. As well as it is the degree of the employee feel devote to the organization (Akintayo,2010a). There are three attitudes of the individuals who committed to theirorganization, they are a feeling of identification of organizational goals, a feeling of volving the duties of the orgamzanon and a sense of loyalty to the organization (Jabeen et al., 2015). On the other hand, the organizational commitment is the psychological status of particular employee about the organization.

Theories on Organizational Commitment

- Side Bet Theory

This theory introduced by the Howard Becker in 1960. This theory explained the collection of investments that are loss if a person leave from the organization. That investments are valued by the individuals subjectively. These investments include income, networks, status and seniority. The individuals know that if they leave the organization, they have to abandon these investments and also it is difficult to find alternative job opportunities in the labor market. Therefore, the individuals committed to their organization. According to that the reason for organizational commitment of individuals are these investments and scarcity of alternative job opportunities (Cohen,2013).

2.2.7. Approaches of Organizational Commitment

Organizational Behavior Approach (Psychology Approach)

This approach considers the organizational commitment as attitudinal or affective. Employees identified the goals, objectives and values of the organization and therefor they committed to the employing organization. Furthermore, there were three dimensions of the organizational commitment under this approach. They are,

- Wish to continue the membership of the organization.
- Identify and accept the values and goals of the organization
- Desire to strive on behalf of the organization.
- This commitment can also be termed as affective commitment and value commitment,

Multi — Dimensional Approach

Multi- dimensional approach presented by John P. Meyer and Natalie Jean Allen in 1984. This approach provides a better understanding to organizational commitment. They found two dimensions of organizational commitment. First one is affective commitment. They defined it as the feeling of bond attachment and identification towards the organization. The second one was continuance commitment. It is the employee commitment toward the organization based on the cost of leaving the organization and difficulty to find alternative job opportunities. Later the researcher adds the third dimension of organizational commitment. It was normative commitment means that employees' feeling obligation to continue the employment with the organization.

2.2.8. Components of Organizational Commitment

Affective Commitment

Affective commitment is employees' psychological attachment and involvement in organization (Meyer, Irving, & Allen, 2014). It is the extent that individuals attach with the organization. On the other hand, it is the emotional bond between employee and the organization. The employees' sense of belongingness, devotion and stability (Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch, & Topolnytsky, 2002). As a result of that the workers aware about the goals and objectives of the organization and act in a way to achieve them (Liu, 2006). Affective commitment cannot be created by force. It creates according to the individuals wish. If the workers have strong affective commitment to organization, they are more likely to retain in the organization. Organizations can attain and improve workers emotional bond to the organization by focusing four aspects of psychological authorization. They are competence, meaning, self-determination and impact (Khan, Nawaz, & Khan, 2013). The organizations should provide a freedom to their employees to get the decision to determine the way to complete the task relating to their jobs.

Continuance Commitment

Primary link of employees to the organization is based on the continuance commitment. Continuance commitment creates within the employees because of the material benefits they are gain from staying with the organization. On the other hand they have to give up these benefits if they leave the job (Meyer et al., 2002). More specifically employees are retain in the organization because of the non –transferable investments they gain from the organization. These benefits are close relationship with peers, retirement benefits, career investments, specific skills that are unique to the current job, years of service and other cost for find another job opportunity elsewhere (Adekola, 2012). That is why they loyal to the organization. Otherwise, they have to give up these benefits and bear the cost of leaving.

Normative Commitment

The social norms of the individuals to the extent they ought to be committed to the organization is affective commitment. Further this is depend on the employees' sense about the social norms. If they feel that they ought to be committed to the organization, they retain in the organization. In other words, it reflects employees feeling of obligation to continue employment (Meyer et al., 2002). The employee who receives benefits from the organization, then there is a social obligation to repay it in some way.

As an example if the organization give a training to employee and then employee feels that he/she has a responsibility to repay it by continuing the job with the organization. Normative commitment reflects an internalized value of the individual to loyal to one's organization that are learned from their parents or society. On the other hand if the organization treat their employees well by being loyal to them it will affect to improve the normative commitment of employees towards the organization (Khan et al., 2013).

2.2.9. Work - Life Conflict and Organizational Commitment

Prior Researches on Study Variables

(Perrewé et al., 1995) conducted a research to build a fundamental investigation of the relationship between stressors, sources of conflict and commitment of the employees in Hong Kong and United States. In here they found that, the work — life conflict is strongly correlated with organizational commitment. Further he stated that there is a negative relationship between these two variables. As well as the research conducted by Netemeyer, Boles, and McMurrian (1996) found that there is a significant negative correlation between work- family conflict and family —work conflict (Work- Life conflict) and organizational commitment of small business owners, high school and elementary school teachers and real estate people in large southeastern city.

Akintayo (2010) conducted a research on Work-family role conflict and organizational commitment among industrial workers in Nigeria. The finding of this study is there was a significant relationship between work — life conflict and organizational commitment. As well as he found a significant difference of work life conflict among men and women industrial workers and also between married and single workers. (Riaz & Hunjra, 2015) conducted a research to find the impact of work — life conflict on organizational commitment among faculty members of different universities in Pakistan. They found that there is a significant negative relationship between work —life conflict and organizational commitment. Further they revealed that the facets of work -life conflict have significant and negative impact on organizational commitment.

The study conducted to find the impact of work- family conflict on organizational commitment of faculty members in private and public Universities in Pakistan by Rehman & Waheed, (2012) found that there is a negative relationship between work- family conflict on organizational commitment. Further they examined the difference of the work =Family conflict face by men and women, single and married members. According to that they exposed married members experienced high level of work-

family conflict than single individuals. Also, there was no significant differences between men and women. Mathias et al., (2010) conducted research to examine the relationship between work- family climate, organizational leadership characteristics, organizational commitment and turnover intent of 526 employees in 37 hotels across US. They revealed a significant relation between work — family climate with organizational commitment and turnover intent.

2.2.10. Work-Life Balance

Enrichment Theory

For most of its history WLB studies were dominated by conflict-oriented perspective but there has been a change in the contemporary perspective as researchers have started to look into the potential symbiotic relationship between work and life. Enrichment theory was developed by Powell & Greenhaus (2006) in order to analyze the phenomenon of enrichment processes that link work to family and family to work. Enrichment is defined as a process that occurs when experience in one role improves the quality of life in another role. Alternatively, it can also be defined as accumulation of psychological resources in a given role that are spilt over into another role (Carlson, Ferguson, Kacmar, Grzywacz, & Whitten, 2011). The model has been posited to be bidirectional as both family-to-work enrichment and work-to-family enrichment have been shown to occur by researchers. Although many similar constructs like facilitation and positive spillover have been used interchangeably with enrichment but there is a fundamental difference. Enrichment represents acquiring the resources and experiences that are useful for individuals facing challenges of life. Thus,

enrichment theory suggests that enhancing of role performance in one domain is dependent upon gaining of resources in another domain.

On the other hand, positive spillover describes transference of experiences, skills, moods and behaviors from one domain to another. A fundamental difference between the two concepts is that transferred experiences in spillover may not necessarily improve the life or increase the performance of the individual in another domain (Carlson, Kacmar, Wayne, & Grzywacz, 2006). Facilitation is assumed to take place when engaging in one domain produces gains that enhance the functioning of another life domain. The distinction between enrichment and facilitation is that of the level at which the analysis is done. Enrichment focuses on the individual quality of life whereas the facilitation delves into improving the functioning of the system (Carlson et al., 2006). Powell & Greenhaus (2006) assert that enrichment may occur along with one of the two pathways viz; Affective path and Instrumental path. Affective work-life enrichment occurs when workers transfer positive behavior and emotions between work and family. Instrumental work-life enrichment occurs when skills and behaviors gained in one domain increase the performance and effectiveness of that individual in another domain. Powell & Eddleston (2011) add family derived enrichment to the mix.

Family derived enrichment occurs when the family members of worker support and assist him/her in work. Carlson et al (2006) improvising on Greenhaus and Powell's model describe a four-dimensional resource gain to measure work-life enrichment namely Developmental, Efficiency, Affective and Capital gains.

Facilitation Theory

Facilitation is defined as "A form of interaction in which resources linked with one role improve or make easier partaking in the other role" (Voydanoff, 2004a). Frone (2003) describes it as the extent to which participation in a role leads to experiences, learning of skills, gaining opportunities which make participation easier in another role. Central to facilitation theory is that performing in a given role is made easier due to participation in another role. Although facilitation is conceived as a theoretical counterpart to work-life conflict but they are not to be considered as opposite poles on the work-life theoretical continuum (van Steenbergen, Kluwer, & Karney, 2014).

The facilitation theory has its beginnings in the study conducted by Barnett (1998) who conceived the idea of facilitation in describing a work-life fit. With the foundation of ecology theory, Grzywacz (2002) explains that facilitation occurs when individuals and social systems use given means to achieve higher complexity (which is their inherent tendency) (Grzywacz & Butler, 2005). Facilitation may occur bi-directionally i.e. from work to family and family to work although both are conceived as being distinct. Wayne, Grzywacz, Carlson, & Kacmar (2007) posit that facilitation consists of three components namely engagement, gains and enhanced functioning. He further defines engagement as degree to which an individual invests in the respective domain activities. The gains are characterized as development gains (acquisition of skills, knowledge etc.), affective gains (Alteration in moods, behavior etc.), capital gains (Monetary, health, social assets) and efficiency gains. Enhanced functioning is defined as enhancements in functions that are fundamental performance in a domain, e.g. problem-solving. Van Steenbergen et al. (2014) have described facilitation along four themes: energy-based facilitation, time-based facilitation, behavior-based facilitation and psychological facilitation. Positive spillover and facilitation both relate to how an individual functioning in one domain can seek the benefits of that in another domain but facilitation occurs not only through personal gains but through capital gains as well (Hammer, Kossek, Yragui, Bodner, & Hanson, 2009).

Segmentation and Integration Theories

Originally termed by Nippert-Eng, (1996) as a 'segmentation preferences', segmentation-integration continuum theory is a model with high role integration and high role segmentation as poles. The segmentation model asserts that work and non-work have no influence on each other and the two domains are distinct (Guest, 2002). Piotrkowski (1979) asserts that segmentation between work and life is brought about when people suppress work-related moods, behaviors and habits in the life domain and act similarly at work by restraining personal behaviors, emotions, thoughts or pleasures. Segmentation is therefore the total separation of the two domains of work and life. In its earlier form, segmentation was perceived along natural/physical locus but contemporary research has shown that segmentation is an active psychosocial process which divides the two worlds (Roy, 2016). Segmentation and integration have been conceptualized as two poles on a continuum of work life balance (Ashforth et al., 2000).

Integration theory refers to a holistic view that presence of flexible boundaries between work and non-work can facilitate a healthier family-life, work-life and community life domains (Clark, 2000). Morris & Madsen (2007) have sought to incorporate additional contextual elements like community into the integration theory stating that "Integration calls for contemporary understandings that reengineer traditional work-life paradigms making all

stakeholders viz employees, workers, families and communities as active partners” Zerubavel (1991) distinguishes between ‘Segmenters’ and ‘Integrators’. He defines

‘Segmenters’ as those individuals who seek to keep two domains apart by creating a mental fence. These people keep work at work place and home at home. He further defines integrators as those individuals who integrate the elements of both domains while removing any barriers between the two. Ashforth et al. (2000) point out to the finding that work may be integrated into non-work and vice versa but the two phenomena take place independently. Along the same lines Nippert-Eng, (1996b) defines high role integration and high role segmentation. High role integration refers to a state when there is no distinction as to what belongs to home and what belongs to work. High role segmentation exists when the two domains are thought of and treated as separate. Any role may fall upon the integration-segmentation continuum with high role segmentation and high role integration as two extremes on this continuum.

Compensation Theory

This theory describes that individuals, because of the lack of fulfilment in one domain, seek compensation in another domain. This theory also asserts that both work and family share the same environment and that family and work have a compensating effect on each other (Mathew & Natarajan, 2014). The compensation has been described as a negative relationship between work and family. It has been termed as negative because negative experiences in one domain result in perception of other domain positively. According to Edwards & Rothbard (2000), two forms of compensation are known. The first one is characterized by decreasing participation in the dissatisfying aspect of life and increased participation in a satisfying domain. Alternatively, a person may respond to dissatisfaction in one domain by pursuing rewards in another. Rewards being those experiences that fulfil individuals’ desires which may further enhance his/her satisfaction. This form of compensation has been further characterized as Supplemental and Reactive compensation. Supplemental compensation occurs when the rewards are insufficient in one domain and they are sought in another domain. Reactive compensation occurs when undesirable experiences are redressed by desirable experience in another domain (Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). Although compensation and enrichment may be construed in a similar manner but the two are fundamentally different. In case of compensation lack of satisfaction in one domain leads to an enhanced focus in other domain while searching for positive feedback, whereas in case of enrichment skills and values in one domain enhance the experience in another domain (Roy, 2016).

Instrumental Theory

Developed as a concept of instrumentality which is defined as: “Work and career are primarily ways of obtaining the means to build and maintain a satisfying and successful family and leisure life; or vice versa” (Evans & Bartolomé, 1984). The basic idea here is that activities conducted in one sphere facilitates activities in other one, for example, a worker who works to maximize earnings even at the time-cost of working for long hour (Guest, 2002).

Congruence Theory

The congruence theory is based on the idea that there is congruence or similarity between work and family and that this similarity is mediated through another variable like genetic factors, personality, traits, socio-cultural forces etc. (Zedeck, 1992). According to congruence theory, a third variable such as genetic factors or community cohesion could positively influence both work and family domains (Mathew & Natarajan, 2014). Although it is very similar to spillover theory, the fundamental difference between the two is that in spillover there is a direct relationship between the work and family whereas in congruence theory it is mediated by a third variable (Edwards & Rothbard, 2000).

Ecological Systems Theory

Ecological theory describes the work-life balance by examining the ecological relationships in the worker’s ecosystem (Pocock, Skinner & Ichii, 2009). The worker ecosystems are conceived as microsystems being located in greater exosystems. It suggests that Work and Family represent a product of process, person, context, time which together yield an additive consequence on the experience of work and life (Grzywacz & Marks, 2000b). Beaujot (2017) basing their assumptions on the ecological theory, seek to work out the relationships between families and economic environment. They elaborate this model by describing earning and caring as two of the most important activities of the families. These activities adapt and change with changing circumstances of the families. Another improvisation on this theory is the person-in-environment theory, which posits that individuals have a dynamic relationship with their physical, social and natural environments (Pitt-Catsoupes & Swanberg, 2006).

Ladder Theory

Conceived by (Bird, 2006), ladder theory asserts that there are two aspects to the work-life balance, first the individual and second the organization. Their roles can be described as two legs of the ladder where the left leg stands for the obligations of the organization for the employees and the right leg stands for the responsibilities of the employees towards the organization. The two legs are joined by the steps namely Profits, Revenue, Commitment, Customer Service, Morale, Productivity, Retention and Recruitment. Such that for an employee the journey ends at the last step (Profits) while starting at recruitment. For balanced work and life both the legs need to be properly functioning.

2.2.11. Job Performance

Employee job performance refers to an employee's expertise in carrying out their duties in a way that helps the organization achieve its goals (Luthans et al., 2007, 2008; Nohe et al., 2014; Moonsri, 2018). It is also defined as an individual's productivity compared to their coworkers on a variety of job-related behaviors and results (Babin and Boles, 1998; Aeknarajindawat and Jermsittiparsert, 2020). Performance is determined by the quality and quantity of work completed as part of an employee's assigned responsibilities. Employee performance directly influences an organization's financial and non-financial outcomes (Anitha, 2014). Thus, organizations need high-performing employees to achieve their corporate goals, vision, and mission and gain a competitive advantage (Thevanes and Mangaleswaran, 2018).

A business must have a persistent competitive advantage in the SME context with many competitors to compete with other companies in the same industry. While job stress has been shown to have a significant negative impact on employee performance, work overload, lack of work-life balance, management style, and job insecurity are some of the factors that contribute to increased job stress (Naqvi et al., 2013). Since SMEs need employees to work longer hours, it is possible that SMEs' employees lack a healthy balance between work and family life, thereby impacting their job performance. Organizations are increasingly focusing on implementing a variety of HR practices and strategies, including work-life balance, on increasing employee job performance, as work-life balance is seen as one of the most important factors influencing job performance (Thevanes and Mangaleswaran, 2018). Previous research found ample evidence that work-life balance is essential to increasing employee job performance (Preena, 2021). Therefore, the role of work-life in influencing SME employees' job performance should be determined to ensure the industry's survival.

2.2.12. Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, and Job Performance

Work-life balance refers to balancing one's professional work, family responsibilities, and other personal activities (Keelan, 2015; Kerdpitak and Jermsittiparsert, 2020). It refers to an employee's sense of a balance between work and personal life (Haar et al., 2014). It represents how people fulfill or should fulfill their business and personal obligations so that an overlapping situation is avoided (Konrad and Mangel, 2000). The changing work patterns and the pressing demand for domestic chores have had an adverse impact on people's work, social, and family lives (Barling and Macewen, 1992). Therefore, researchers suggested that the human resource management of an organization should develop effective policies such as adequate mentoring, support, flexible working hours, reducing workload, and many others that can reduce employees' work-life conflict (Cegarra-Leiva et al., 2012) and positively influence their satisfaction (Allen et al., 2020) and performance (Hughes and Bozionelos, 2007).

Work-life balance is one of the most important issues that human resource management should address in organizations (Abdirahman et al., 2020). Regardless of their size, organizations should ensure that employees have adequate time to fulfill their family and work commitments (Abdirahman et al., 2020). A flexible working environment allows employees to balance personal and professional responsibilities (Redmond et al., 2006). Organizations that ignore the issue of work-life balance suffer from reduced productivity and employee performance (Naithani, 2010). Indeed, employees with a healthy work-life balance are generally grateful to their employers (Roberts, 2008). As a result, they put forth their best effort for the company as a gesture of gratitude, resulting in improved job performance (Ryan and Kossek, 2008). Thus, a high work-life balance employee could be highly productive and an excellent performer (French et al., 2020). Thus, based on these discussions and research findings, we developed the following

2.2.13. Family Supportive Supervisor Behaviors

Hammer et al. (2009) define family-supportive supervisor behaviors (FSSB) as the emotional, instrumental, role-modeling, and creative work-family management supportive behaviors that the supervisors provide to ensure employee effectiveness and satisfaction on and off the job. It refers to an employee's perception of their supervisor's positive attitude toward them (Clark et al., 2017). Supervisory support could be formal or informal (Achour et al., 2020). It is critical in developing flexible work arrangements (Suriana et al., 2021).

Supervisory supportive behavior is very important for ensuring work-life balance and achieving organizational goals. It has been shown to reduce work-family spillover (García-Cabrera et al., 2018) by increasing employee job satisfaction autonomy and reducing work pressure (Marescaux et al., 2020). The flexibility and independence generated by FSSB help to reduce work-family conflict (Greenhaus et al., 2012) by increasing employees' control over their work (Marescaux et al., 2020) and allowing them to strike a balance between their work and family life (Heras et al., 2021).

Employees who believe their managers care about their personal and professional lives are more likely to improve their performance and meet supervisory objectives (Rofcanin et al., 2018). In a university-based study, Achour et al. (2020) showed how supervisory support positively moderates the relationship between a female academic's work-family demands and perceived well-being. Kim et al. (2017) show that supervisory support can strengthen the relationship between deep acting and job performance, exacerbating the negative relationship between surface acting and job performance. Therefore, this study argues that, in an organization, when work-life balance is valued, supervisory support might influence employees' positive perception, and the effect of work-life balance strategies and job satisfaction on job performance will be greater.

2.3. Empirical Literature

2.3.1. Work Life Balance

Work-Life Balance (WLB) has its beginnings in the nineteenth century after a long campaign of workers against long working hours in the factories (Hogarth & Bosworth, 2009). This was carried further into the early twentieth century when several labor unions campaigned for a cap on the maximum working hours (Myers, 1924). A significant moment in the history of WLB was when President F.D. Roosevelt signed the Fair Labor Standards Act of 1938. This act ushered in some far-reaching changes in the work regimes e.g. prohibition of the child labor, setting a minimum hourly wage, regulations to determine and record overtimes and setting maximum work week at 44 hours per week (which was later reduced to 40 hours in 1940) (Sullivan, 2014). The research in the field of work-life balance began in 1960s, when several researches were conducted focusing on working mothers and dual-earner families owing to the increase in the participation of women in the workforce (Lewis, Gambles, & Rapoport, 2007). The work of Rapport and Rapport in the 1960s was pioneering in this field. It focused on the segmentation of work and family caused by rural to urban movement of workforce (Naithani, 2010).

Before the 1970s, 'work' and 'family' were perceived as mutually exclusive domains but Kanter (1977) emphasized the fundamental interconnectedness of the two by highlighting how work affects the family and vice versa. Along the same lines, Pleck (1995) defined what he termed as spillover as a phenomenon where work role affects the family role and contrariwise. He further states, in the same study, that women experience spillover from family to work whereas men experience it from work to family. Continuing the research in this field, in the 1980s two new theories came to the fore. Staines (1980), described the relationship between work and family through compensation theory. As per the compensation theory a worker seeks to compensate the deficit in one aspect of life (in this case, work or family) by compensating in the other aspect i.e. by expending more resources in the other aspect. Greenhaus & Beutell (1985) came up with conflict theory which states that the aspects of work and life are contrasting in nature and in demanding effort and time these two aspects compete for an individual's attention. By late 1980s various human resource practitioners started to present work-life balance as primarily a 'business issue' and the organizations across the board began to perceive that investing resources into WLB was for the greater good of the organization and the employee (Frame & Hartog, 2003). While the first wave of programs was addressed to support working mothers, in the 1990s, a growing need was felt that the work/life programs be directed to the commitments of everyone including women, men, parents, non-parents, singles and couples (Lockwood, 2003).

3. Methodology

3.1. Introduction

This chapter provide the descriptions about the "Research methodology" used to conduct the study. It provides an explanation about research approach research context unit of analysis, population and sample, data collection, methods of data collection and data analysis.

3.1.1. Conceptualization

Based on the literature review the conceptual frame work is illustrated as following.

Figure 2 Conceptual Frame Work

Source: Author constructs after reviewing literature

3.2. Research Approach

A researcher can conduct the research by using two approaches. It can be qualitative approach or quantitative approach. A deep understanding can be get from the qualitative approach, When conducting a qualitative research the aim is to interpret and understand the phenomena by asking questions such as “whom, how and why.” Quantitative researches are mostly conducted to test the existing theories of the phenomena. The main purpose is to gather, analysis and measure statistical data. This research also attempts to test existing theory. Therefore, this research falls on the category of quantitative research.

3.3. Research Context

The purpose of this study is to find the relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment of nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district, Sri Lanka. Therefore, the research context of this study is the public sector hospitals in Galle district.

3.4. Population and Sample

Population refers to the entire group of people, events, or things of interest that the researcher wishes to investigate. According to the purpose of this research, the target population of this study is all the nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle District. According to the annual health statistics conducted by medical statistical unit there are 1485 nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district. The selected hospitals have 780 nurses .Therefor the sample is 120.

3.5. Sampling Method

A sample is a sub set or the population. It comprises some members selected form the population. The researcher used convenience sampling method to select the sample from the population. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling method. Sample is selected from a group of people easy to contact or reach.

Table 1 The Target population and Sample

Population of the selected hospitals	780
Sample	120

Source: Annual Health statistics, Medical Statistical Unit, Ministry of Health

3.6. Data Collection Method

Data can be obtained through primary and secondary sources. Primary data refers to information obtained first hand by the researcher on the variable of interest for the specific purpose of the study (Sekaran and Bougie 2013). Sekaran and Bougie (2013) has defined Secondary data as the information gathered from the sources that are already existing. Both data collection techniques will be referred in this research study.

3.6.1. Primary Data

Primary data has been collected through either Experiment or through Survey. To collect primary data researcher use self-administered questionnaire method and hand delivery method use to distribute questionnaire. Due to the busy work schedules of nurses it is really difficult to conduct individual interview. Therefore the researcher decided to use questionnaire method.

Organization of questionnaire

Questionnaire is standardized set of questions to collect data from the selected respondents. Questionnaire consists with four sections. The section I consists of Demographic information covered by Age, Marital status, Number of children, Are your parents or spouse’s parents living with you?, How long have you been this organization?. Section II consist of six questions to test work interference

with family, Section III consist of six questions to test Family interference with work and section IV was designed to test Organizational Commitment. A five point Likert scale has been used in this second section of the questionnaire to measure the relationship between work -life conflict and organizational commitment. The scaling 1s: 5 for strongly agree, 4 for agree, 3 for neutral, 2 for disagree and | for strongly disagree have been given in order to analyze data.

Measurement of work- life conflict

The researcher expected to measure the work life conflict in two dimensions: work interference with family, family interference with work. Work life conflict measurement scales developed by ((Kopelman et al., 1983; Netemeyer et al., 1996) used to measure the independent variable.

Measurement of organizational commitment

The researcher used 3 dimensions to measure the organizational commitment as indicated in literature review. They are affective organizational commitment, normative organizational commitment, and continuance organizational commitment. According to that organizational commitment scales developed by (Meyer & Allen, 2004; Mowday, Steers, & Porter, 1979). The details of measurements scales are used in this study is mentioned in the table 2.

Table 2 Title Measurement of Variables

Variable	Dimension	Question Number	Source
Work –life conflict	Work interference with family	1,2,3,4,6	(Netemryer et al.,1996)
		5	(Kopelman et al.,1983)
	Family interference with work	1,3,4,5,6	-
		2	(Kopelman et al.,1983)
Organizational commitment	Affective commitment	1,2,4,5	(Mowday, steers& porter ,1979)
	Continuance Commitment	6	(Meyer& Allen , 2004)
	Normative commitment	3	(Meyer& Allen , 2004)

Source : Author originated source

3.6.2. Secondary Data

Secondary data means already published and reported data which used for study. Annual Health statistics, Medical Statistical Unit, Ministry of Health use to collect data with regard to the total population of nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district and based on that population the researcher determined the sample. Secondary data collects from the journal articles, text books and web sites.

3.7. Ethical Consideration

The ethical considerations must be an integral aspect of any study according to Creswell (2009). Dependable ethical principles were observed in the course of conducting the research. Sauderse (2009) adds that gaining permission and

consent to collect data is a very important aspect of any study. In all data collection however, researcher’s University ID card was shown. Next to this, participants were fully informed regarding the objectives of the study, while they were reassured that their answers were treated as confidential and used only for academic purposes and only for the purposes of particular research.

4. Data analysis

4.1. Introduction

This chapter will present the summary of the collected data through questionnaires from nurses in public hospitals of Galle District. The Microsoft Excel 2013 version used to analyze the data. This chapter analyzes the data and present key findings relating to the survey. The chapter gives details regarding presentation of collected data through various sources. Data presentation includes only survey data (primary data). The chapter includes the analysis of the data which were analyzed using statistical models, techniques and tools. In the first part the researcher analyzes the demographic information. Then researcher test the reliability to test the internal consistency of the variables to the concepts. Then analyze the correlation using correlation analysis.

- Presentation of Demographic Information
- Age Distribution

Table 3 Age distribution

Age	Frequency	Percent %
18- 25	32	26.7%
26- 35	51	42.5%
36- 44	23	19.2%
More than 45	14	11.7%
Total	120	100

Source: Survey data 2024

According to the data on table 3, there were 26.7% respondents represented in age range 18-25 years and 42.5%, 19.2%, 11.7% included in age range 26-35, 36-44, more than 45 years respectively. Most of the respondents are in age range 26-35 years. Age category of more than 45 years represent the lowest number of respondents. It is 11.7%

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Figure 3 Age Distribution

4.1.1. Marital Status of Respondents

The researcher collected data from both married and single nurses for this research. The marital status distribution of the sample presented as table 4.

Table 4 Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent %
Married	84	70
Single	36	30
Total	120	100

Source: Survey Data, 202

As indicated by table 4, 84 respondents are married out of 120 respondents, which is 70% of the total respondents. 36 are single, which is 30% of the total respondents. According to that majority of the respondents of the sample are married.

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Figure 4 Marital Status

4.1.2. Number of Children

Table 5 Number of Children

No of children	frequency	Percent %
No children	47	39.2
Only one child	36	30
Two children	23	19.2
Three children	13	10.8
More than three children	01	0.8
Total	120	100

Source: Survey Data, 2024

According to the data represented in table 5, 47 respondents haven't children which is 39.2% of the total respondents. 36 respondents have only one child. 23 respondents have two children. 13 respondents have 13 children only one respondent have more than three children

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Figure 5 Number of Children

4.1.3. Weather the Parents are living Together with Respondent

Question number 4 in the questionnaire was “Are your parents or spouse's parents living with you?” gathered data on this question is presented in the table 6

Table 6 Weather the Parents are Living Together with Respondent

scale	Frequency	Percent %
Yes	57	47.5
No	63	52.5
Total	120	100

Source: Survey Data, 2024

According to table 6, 57 respondents living together with their parents. It is 47.5% of the total respondents. 63 respondents are not living together with their parents. Therefore, most of the respondents are not living with their parents.

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Figure 6 Whether the Respondents Living Together with Parents

4.1.4. Service period of Respondents

Question number 5 in the questionnaire was “How long have you been this organization?” gathered data on this question is presented in the table 7.

Table 7 Service period of Respondents.

Service period	Frequency	Percent %
Less than 1 year	13	10.8
1 to 4 year	40	33.3
5 to 10 year	38	31.7
11 to 14 year	19	15.8
More than 15 year	10	8.3
Total	120	100

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Table 7 indicated that most of the respondents (40) have | to 4 year service period and 10 workers have more than 15 year service experience. It is 8.3% of the total respondents. Also 38 respondents have 5 to 10 year service experience. It is 31.7% of the total sample. The graphical representation of the Above data are as follows.

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Figure 7 Service Period of Respondents

4.1.5. Work Interference with Family

According to data analysis of the chapter four it was observed there is a negative relationship between work interference with family of nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district Sri Lanka. Bellow analysis are based on section 2 of the questionnaire. According to the above chart

In Question No 1: 44.1% responses have disagreed and 14.1% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly disagreed for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work interference with family.

In Question No 2: 45.8% responses have disagreed and 15% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work interference with family.

In Question No 3: 27.5% responses have disagreed and 14.1% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work interference with family.

In Question No 4: 44.1% responses have disagreed and 14.1% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work interference with family

In Question No 5: 45% responses have disagreed and 26.8% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work interference with family

In Question No 6: 44.1% responses have disagreed and 14.1% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work interference with family

Figure 8 Work Interference with Family

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Family Interference with Work According to data analysis of the chapter four it was observed there is a negative relationship between family interference with work of nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district Sri Lanka . Bellow analysis are based on section 3 of the questionnaire. According to the above chart

In Question No 1: 44.1% responses have disagreed and 14.1% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between family interference with work.

In Question No 1: 45.8% responses have disagreed and 15% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between family interference with work

In Question No 1: 27.5% responses have disagreed and 14.1% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between family interference with work.

In Question No 1: 44.1% responses have disagreed and 14.1% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between family interference with work.

In Question No 1: 45% responses have disagreed and 20.8% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between family interference with work.

In Question No 1: 44.1% responses have disagreed and 14.1% responses have strongly disagreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between family interference with work.

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Figure 9 Family Interference with Work

4.1.6. Organizational Commitment

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Figure 10 Organizational Commitment

According to data analysis of the chapter four it was observed there is a negative relationship between family interference with work of nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district Sri Lanka . Bellow analysis are based on section 4 of the questionnaire. According to the above chart

In Question No 1: 70% responses have agreed and 8.33% responses have strongly agreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment.

In Question No 2: 65% responses have agreed and 5.8% responses have strongly agreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment.

In Question No 3: 66.6% responses have agreed and 6.6% responses have strongly agreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment.

In Question No 4: 65% responses have agreed and 4.1% responses have strongly agreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment.

In Question No 5: 66.6% responses have agreed and 4.1% responses have strongly agreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment.

In Question No 6: 70% responses have agreed and 8.33% responses have strongly agreed. That percentage is higher than people who have agreed and strongly for the above question in the questionnaire .it means there is a negative relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment.

5. Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between work — life Conflict and organizational commitment among female nurses in public sector hospitals of Galle district, Sri Lanka. The outcomes of testing research are proved that all the hypothesis are accepted according to the numerical data . So this section devotes discussion of findings of this study. When consider the demographic information of the sample the age of 42.5%of respondents are in the range of 26-35 years and.70% are married respondents and 39.2% of the respondents haven't children and 30% of the respondents have only one child, 52.5% respondents are not living together with their parents and 33.3% respondents have 1 to 4 years work experience.

The summary of the results of hypotheses which were tested in this study is presented that there is a negative relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment.

5.1. Relationship Between Work Life Conflict and Organizational Commitment

Based on the data analysis results of the study, there is a significant negative relationship between work life conflict and organizational commitment of nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district Sri Lanka

5.2. Findings of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between work — life Conflict and organizational commitment among female nurses in public sector hospitals of Galle district, Sri Lanka.. Based on the research purpose researcher developed the conceptual framework after reviewing literature to test the above mentioned relationship. According to the research findings researcher has found that there is a significant negative relationship between work - life conflict and organizational commitment among nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district Sri Lanka.

6. Conclusion and recommendation

6.1. Introduction

Objective of this chapter is to give conclusion based on findings of this study and then provide recommendations and summary of the study. In addition to that the researcher expect to indicate the limitations of the study and based on the limitations the directions to future studies are provides in this chapter.

6.2. Conclusion and Recommendation

Main objective of this study 1s to investigate the relationship between work — life Conflict and organizational commitment among female nurses in public sector hospitals of Galle district, Sri Lanka. Research problem addressed by this study is what is the relationship between work - life conflict and organizational commitment among nurses in public sector hospitals of Galle district, Sri Lanka?

The data was collected by using questionnaires for the selected sample of nurses in public sector hospitals of Galle district, Sri Lanka. After that collected data were analyzed using Excel 2013 version. According to the findings of the study conclusion can be presented as follows.

When consider the two determinants of work — life conflict; work interference with family and family interference with work has significant negative relationship with organizational commitment of Nurses. The work life conflict as a whole also has a significant negative relationship with organizational commitment. Finally the researcher can conclude that there is a significant negative relationship between work —life conflict and organizational commitment of nurses in public sector hospitals of Galle district, Sri Lanka.

Therefore the nurses should aware about the importance of balancing their work and family roles to create a psychological bond with their hospital. Ultimately it will affect to reduce the other negative outcomes such as pressure, stress, mental ill-health, job dissatisfaction, marital dissatisfaction and total life dissatisfaction. The hospital administrations has to get steps to improve the organizational support for the nurses to Balance their two domains of the life to increase the commitment of them toward the hospitals. Because committed employees positively contributed to the organization compared to less committed employees. Not only for the organizational success, 1s the commitment of nurses very critical to the society as a whole to increase the health of the country.

6.3. Summary of the Study

Purpose of this research study is to investigate the relationship between work — life Conflict and organizational commitment among female nurses in public sector hospitals of Galle district, Sri Lanka. Independent variables are work — life conflict; work interference with family, family interference with work. Data were collected from 120 Nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district through self- administered questionnaire and questionnaire was distributed by using convenience sampling method. The researcher analyzed the collected data by using Excel 2013 version. When researcher analyzing and presenting data, mainly used the frequency distribution analysis, reliability analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis and these were used . The researcher has found there were significant negative relationship between independent and dependent variables.

6.4. Findings

The researcher supposed to provide some recommendations for further researchers who interested doing research in the same field based on the limitations of this study This study focus only on the nurses in public sector hospitals in Galle district. It is better to choose nurses in public and private sector hospitals to do comparison study about the topic. As well as this study focus only on the one type of respondent category in the health industry. The future researchers are recommended for focus on other employees in health care sector to achieve better results. Not only limiting to quantitative data (using qualitative data) will be a good technique for future researches. Collecting data by interviewing employees is a good data collection method. Because employees will provide their real ideas for the researcher. The sample size of this study is small. Therefore the researcher recommend to expand the sample size to increase the generalizability of the results for future researchers.

Abbreviations

WLB: Work-Life Balance

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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